

The yield potential of three crosses between diverse parents of indica type

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A widespread belief exists that the yield of indica cultivars grown in the lowland tropics has reached a barrier of 10 t ha⁻¹ because of the narrow genetic base of modern varieties. We tested this hypothesis by evaluating the yield potential of the crosses between high-yielding Sri Lankan varieties and high-yielding IRRRI varieties: Bg34-8/IR58 (cross 1; 3-mo duration), Bg94-1/IR62 (cross 2; 3 1/2 mo duration) and Bg90-2/IR72 (cross 3; 4 1/2 mo duration). Individuals raised were of the basic generations (P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, B₁, and B₂) and F₃ and triple testcross families (F₂ × P₁, F₂ × P₂, and F₂ × F₁) of each of these pedigrees in three completely randomized experiments, one for each cross.

Each of the 14 characters scored was heritable. Estimates of the heritability of grain yield, obtained from F₃ families for

crosses 1, 2, and 3, were 0.29, 0.38 and 0.51, and for 1,000-grain weight over 0.57, 0.58, and 0.70, respectively. Though this was significant only in cross 1, the F₁ mean exceeded that of the best parent in all three crosses for grain yield. The dominance ratio, (H/D)^{1/2}, which was less than one in each cross, indicated that the increasing genes for this character were dispersed between the parents. Predictions of the proportion of recombinant inbred lines that could be extracted by single seed descent from each cross, the performance of which exceeds that of the best parent, showed that it should be relatively easy to obtain such lines from each cross for the majority of characters, including grain yield and 1,000-grain weight.

Estimates of genetic correlations between characters varied considerably over crosses, suggesting that their major cause is the linkage disequilibrium of linked genes rather than pleiotropy. Grain yield was strongly and positively correlated (r ≥ 0.7) with tiller and panicle number, days to heading, height at flowering, and panicle weight in cross 3. However, in cross 2, grain yield was only strongly and positively correlated with number of grains panicle⁻¹ and panicle weight, and in cross 1, with tiller number and panicle number. Results suggest that it should be possible to identify

crosses in a breeding program from which recombinant inbred lines can be extracted that are superior for any combination of traits of a desired multiple phenotype. Upon examining the means of the 38-40 F₃ families raised in these experiments, one or more families achieved the desired target for each of the majority of characters, including grain yield in all three crosses. Evidence of transgressive variation for characters of interest as early as the F₃ generation leaves little doubt about their potential to produce superior inbred lines.

The mean grain yield of the best F₃ family, cross 3, which is in the same age group as the new plant type, was 154.4 g. The predicted yield was 9.7 t ha⁻¹, which is appreciably better than the predicted yield of 8.3 t ha⁻¹ for the best parent of this cross, Bg90-2.

Results from this investigation are inconsistent with the belief that the apparent yield barrier of indica cultivars is due to a narrow genetic base. This suggests that the inability of breeders to breach this barrier is because of other causes, including inefficient breeding procedures and employing indirect visual selection when attempting to obtain improvement for several quantitative characters simultaneously. ■

Stability analysis of 13 early-duration upland rice genotypes in Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Nearly 0.24 million ha of upland rice is grown in Bastar Plateau Zone in Madhya Pradesh during wet season (June-September). Traditional, low-yielding cultivars are dominant in the zone. Suitable upland early rice varieties need to be identified.

We evaluated 13 early-duration rice genotypes for grain yield and morpho-agronomic attributes. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during the 1990-92 wet seasons. Each genotype was direct seeded in ten 5-m long rows using 25-cm spacing. We recorded plant height, panicle length, fertile grains panicle⁻¹, and percentage spikelet fertility for five randomly selected plants from each plot of every replication. Days to flowering, days to maturity, and grain yield were computed for each plot. Number of panicle-bearing tillers m⁻² from a randomly selected 1-m² plot was recorded. Means were used for stability analysis over three environments following the method of Ebberhart and Russel (1966).

Table 1. Mean grain yield (t ha⁻¹) and estimates of stability parameters for 13 rice genotypes across three environments. Jagdalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1990-92.

Genotype	x	b	s ² d
R.281 PP 31-1	1.64	0.88	2.84
RWR 78-71-9	1.97	1.33	4.44
JR80-4-6	1.56	1.34	1.16
JR84-7-1-19	2.19	0.78	8.75
RNR1446	2.07	1.17	-5.88
Culture 1	1.66	-0.03***	-6.59
Poorva	1.34	0.11**	-6.55
Annada	2.55	1.85**	-4.72
Tulasi	2.37	2.01**	-4.75
Rasi	2.19	1.95**	4.22
Aditya	2.14	0.89	3.68
Tellahamsa	2.19	0.87	-0.06
Badoldhan (L)	1.97	-0.16**	-6.28
av		1.99	

*** = significant at the 1% level.

Table 2. Morphoagronomic attributes (av of 3 yr) of upland rice genotypes at Jagdalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India.

Genotype		Days to 50% flowering	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Fertile grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)
R281 PP 31-1	Poorva/IR8608-298	82	109	71	302	19.0	60	86
RWR78-71-9	T3/T141//T3	77	104	76	351	18.2	56	86
JR80-4-6	DR42/Ratna	84	109	66	313	18.5	57	87
JR84-7-1-19	-	72	99	70	261	19.6	65	84
RNR1446	Tellahamsa/Rasi	80	106	81	311	18.8	62	90
Culture 1	AC540/Ratna	67	94	95	324	20.6	61	87
Poorva	Saket 4/JR 2-331	70	97	65	320	17.4	53	86
Annada	MTU15/Waikaku	80	106	71	300	20.4	82	91
Tulasi	Rasi/white gora	81	107	79	305	18.2	66	89
Rasi	TN1/CO 29	83	110	76	316	17.8	64	89
Aditya	M63-83/Cauvery	66	90	75	288	17.8	58	90
Tellahamsa	H12/TN1	81	107	80	279	18.5	66	90
Badoldhan (L)	-	78	104	120	217	22.1	99	93

Regression coefficients (b) ranged from -0.16 to 2.01 (Table 1). The variance due to deviation from regression (s^2d) was -6.59-8.75. The stability parameters of seven genotypes were not significant, indicating they are stable yielders across environments.

Rice varieties Aditya and Tellahamsa had b values close to unity (0.89 and 0.87),

indicating their high stable performance across the environments tested. These varieties yielded above average and have been released for upland cultivation around India. Varieties Annada, Tulasi, and Rasi show slightly above average grain yield (Table 1). These b values were significantly deviated from unity, indicating they were more responsive under favorable environments.

Stability for grain yield in rice appears to be imparted by the stability of most of the yield attributes (Table 2). Genotypes Aditya, Tellahamsa, RNR1446, R281 PP 31-1, and JR84-7-1-19 were stable yielders over time. They are recommended for upland cultivation in Bastar Plateau Zone and for use in breeding cultivars with yield potential and adaptability. ■

Variability, heritability, genetic advance, and genetic divergence in upland rice

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Attempts to improve rice cultivars grown in the upland ecosystem have been limited. Systematic evaluation of the genetic variability and divergence of the existing upland rice germplasm is, therefore, important.

We studied genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advance, and genetic divergence of

39 upland rice genotypes. Most of them were early-maturing indigenous cultivars from Madhya Pradesh, India. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with three replications, during 1993 kharif (dry) season.

The significant mean sum of squares indicated the strong variability among the

Table 1. Genetic parameters of variation in upland rice. BHU, Varanasi, India. 1993.

Parameter	Traits											
	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Primary branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Secondary branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	100-grain weight (g)	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain length (mm)	Effective tillers m ⁻¹ row length (no.)	Grain yield m ⁻¹ row length (g)
Range: Minimum	66.3	87.3	62.4	4.7	6.6	1.6	0.6	15.3	37.6	6.2	36.7	17.5
Maximum	96.3	124.3	108.2	10.4	32.2	2.8	3.1	25.0	158.0	9.9	251.0	82.0
Genotypic variance	47.0	85.2	198.3	1.3	27.3	0.1	0.3	4.4	576.7	0.8	1066.5	198.0
Phenotypic variance	50.7	100.1	211.1	1.8	33.9	0.1	0.3	6.9	636.4	0.8	1518.1	469.6
Genotypic coefficient of variation	8.6	8.6	15.9	13.5	28.8	13.2	29.1	9.9	25.4	10.6	44.8	25.9
Phenotypic coefficient of variation	8.9	9.4	16.4	16.2	32.2	13.9	30.8	12.5	26.7	10.6	53.4	39.9
Heritability (%)	92.8	85.1	93.9	69.4	80.4	90.7	89.6	64.0	90.6	99.9	70.2	42.2
Genetic advance (% of mean)	17.1	16.4	31.8	23.2	53.2	25.9	53.9	16.4	49.8	21.9	77.3	35.6
CV (%)	2.4	3.6	4.0	9.0	14.3	4.2	9.9	7.5	8.2	0.4	29.1	30.3